

Development of Physical Culture of Students of Higher Education Institutions

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Abstract:

In the article, the theoretical-methodological foundations and practical means of popularizing sports among students and youth, strengthening their physical activity and health, innovative factors of forming healthy lifestyle skills through the sports factor, the advanced foreign experience in this regard, physical education of our country the need to apply it to education has been researched.

Key words: higher education, student, sport, physical education, healthy life, physical activity, healthy life.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in the world, researching human health, physical fitness and capabilities, studying the impact of physical maturity on human mental and social activity, in particular, the process of improving the physical culture of students of the higher education system, future personnel, is a new scientific-practical pedagogy. A lot of research work is being carried out on the use of innovative methods and technologies in the creation of models and their implementation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

In the higher education system, the knowledge capacity, experience, methodology of training and the systematicity, consistency, and continuity of conducting training are important for developing physical culture of students, discovering the qualities of physical culture. becomes important. In this, of course, the level of professionalism and creativity of the teachers-coaches is harmonious the necessity of their existence and the fact that they have the law of consistently complementing each other and developing is of great importance" [2].

The importance of physical education classes and sports clubs is high in the formation of qualities such as physical will, endurance, striving for victory, dexterity, and self-control in students of the higher education system. The reason is that sportsmen's character and qualities are gradually formed in students through physical education and sports activities, and later these qualities become their permanent quality. For example, a student with well-formed physical volitional qualities will also be volitional in life activities.

This indicates that the student has both strong will and physical character. However, his "stable character traits, positive moral and voluntary qualities are formed in physical education training and competitions, in the process of education and training, in work. Continuous continuation of this process leads to high results. On the contrary, the student's negative qualities such as lack of discipline in class, lack of ability to learn, evasion of studies and work, rudeness or deception lead to his inability to cope with obstacles both in big sports and in life, leading to mental depression. [2; 57,58b].

"The peculiarity of physical education is that it serves as a means of developing physical abilities, and at the same time it has a strong influence on spiritual maturity" [3]. According to Ibn Sina, the best qualities of a person are first of all endurance, wisdom and courage. These positive qualities together create justice and moderation in his character. If a person has these qualities, he will devote himself to good deeds without ever engaging in bad ways. Therefore, every period of life has its own beauty. In this sense, it is necessary for the student to develop his character in order to acquire thorough knowledge, to form universal human qualities, to be active in social life, and to become a person who is not afraid of difficulties. For this, he must achieve the formation of his own character traits:

1. A student of a higher educational institution should get used to showing a state of strong mental activity in all aspects of life.
2. Students must have good morals, deep thinking, a broad worldview, strong physical will, and feelings of health.
3. A student should be conscientious in achieving his goals in life and should be able to create a healthy lifestyle [2].

Some problems in developing the qualities of physical culture among students are also noticeable. For example, some students choose a sport that does not suit their character, or their parents make the choice for them. And this turns off their interest in this sport or club and the desire to act conscientiously. Because some students are recreational, they cannot participate in aggressive sports, or even if they do, the results are not effective.

Special attention should also be paid to the psychological issues of educating students in physical culture. That is, aggressiveness and violence in students can show positive results in sports. But over time, students often face mental difficulties after not being able to stop their "aggressive actions." Because he could not change his behavior, he has a lot of trouble, not being able to live a peaceful life like other people" [4]. Therefore, in order to increase the physical capabilities of students, it is necessary to pay attention to their physical education and sports training, and to direct them to professional sports. However, it is necessary not to become the cause of their mental breakdown and damage and not to create an opportunity for them to admit their lack of will.

Taking into account the importance of physical education and sports, a number of works are being carried out in Uzbekistan to develop a healthy lifestyle and to further improve the work of raising a healthy generation through the development of physical culture.

Physical education can be divided into two groups that are integrated into each other in terms of their specific characteristics.

1. Physical education - influencing physical development, acquiring physical qualities and improving them in order to strengthen health.
2. Physical education - education that provides special skills, abilities and knowledge. The peculiarity of physical education is that it serves as a means of developing physical abilities, and at the same time, it also has a strong influence on spiritual maturity [3].

It is known that the students of the higher educational institution should apply the theoretical knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in the educational process of physical education and sports education, develop personal and voluntary qualities inherent in physical culture, provides an opportunity for independent activity. The analysis of the answers of the respondents showed that there are inaccuracies in the answers of the students of the control group, who in their answers could not adequately assess the possibility of developing physical culture in students through physical education and sports in the higher education system. It can be seen that they did not fully understand the role and tasks of physical culture in the development of a student in higher education.

The respondents-students assigned to the experimental groups were able to correctly express their opinions regarding the given question. However, they could not scientifically justify the importance of physical culture in the process of education in the higher education system. This situation shows that they do not have enough theoretical knowledge.

A few students correctly answered the next question about what physical culture qualities students should possess in order to be a competitive major in their field.

However, "Describe the qualities of physical culture in the student?" The students who are taking physical education classes could not fully answer the question. The reason for this is the subjects of physical education in the educational process

it is not possible to introduce students closely to the characteristics of physical culture and their essence in teaching.

From the content of the questions and answers, it was understood that the students of the control group do not have specific knowledge about the professional and personal qualities that form physical culture, physical education and sports skills, and the importance of pedagogical education technology in the development of physical culture skills. When answering the above questions, they only considered "physical culture" and "willed qualities specific to physical education and sports" as a general concept. The students of the experimental group gave correct and clear answers to the questions, relying on the knowledge given during the experiment-testing process of the research.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Today, there is a need to provide education based on a new approach to the development of physical culture of students and youth, development of physical education and sports, strengthening of health, promotion of a healthy lifestyle. Physical culture, like other forms of culture, is a part of the complex development system of a person. To teach students of higher education institutions to take care of their health, to create a healthy lifestyle in them through playing sports, to form the skills of independent physical education is the main goal of the pedagogical process. Therefore, in the higher education system, in order to develop the mental potential of students, train their mental will, and constantly improve their physical culture, sports games, cycling, table tennis, badminton, chess and checkers, athletics and other sports are organized. inclusion of sports competitions on a regular basis, that is, at least once a quarter, in educational programs, regular national festival "Student Sports Day" among students engaged in sports in an unprofessional manner transfer should be started.

Among the tasks of developing physical culture skills in students, it is important to determine issues aimed at strengthening the health of students and increasing the level of physical development. The pedagogical value of physical education and sports activities is high in the formation of such qualities as willpower, striving for victory, dexterity, self-control, endurance in students. Therefore, it is appropriate to hold sports events and mass physical training events with the participation of sports stars, actively use the sports infrastructure of sports institutions, organize open exercises and autograph sessions for students with the involvement of leading professional trainers.

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